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FOSTERING QUALITY OF REFLECTION IN FIRST-YEAR HONOURS STUDENTS IN A BACHELOR ENGINEERING PROGRAM TECHNOLOGY, LIBERAL ARTS & SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on fostering the quality reflection displayed in semester self-evaluation reports (SERs) of First-year Honours Students in a Bachelor engineering program Technology, Liberal Arts and Science (ATLAS) of the University of Twente in the Netherlands. The underlying problem that inspired this study was that the quality of reflection was considered too low. In addition, there was unclarity in the program on to what was expected of students with respect to reflection. Twenty-nine participants, not previously exposed to academic training on reflection before, received a Reflection Guide on how to write written reflections in their SERs. Two online lectorials (interactive lectures) were provided to elaborate on the content of the guide and to address any questions of the students. Quality of reflection in the SERs was assessed using a standardized rubric and quality scores in the intervention group were compared with scores of the student cohort of the previous academic year ($n = 33$). Results showed that the intervention group reflected significantly on a higher level than the comparison group.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

ATLAS University College Twente is a bachelor of science program in Technology, Liberal Arts & Science that aims at educating the ‘New Engineer’ (Goldberg & Sommerville, 2014). The program has embraced the concept of self-directed learning (Gibbons, 2002; Saks & Leijen, 2014), meaning that students attain learning goals mostly in their own way. Semester goals (there are six semesters) define a developmental framework that allows students to gradually build their own academic profile as New Engineers. At the same time, the framework safeguards that all students reach the intended learning outcomes of the program as a whole. At the start of each semester, students write a plan in which they explain how they intend to reach the semester goals of their current semester. At the end of each semester, students write a self-evaluation report (SER) in which they reflect on their development and evaluate whether they reached the goals of the semester. The SER is input for a semester assessment meeting in which a group of assessors decides to what extent the students’ self-evaluation can be justified. As part of this assessment, students receive feedback on the *quality* of reflection and self-evaluation displayed in their SERs. As a requirement to pass the semester, quality of reflection and self-evaluation needs to be at a sufficient level.

Reflecting and self-evaluating are considered important skills by the program, both for the students’ learning, and for their role as New Engineers in society. New Engineers typically work interdisciplinary, meaning that they need to be able to quickly familiarize themselves with new fields of expertise to be a linking pin in interdisciplinary teams. Actively monitoring what one knows and what still needs to be learned through continuous reflection and self-evaluation is therefore of seminal importance. Life-long learning characterizes the professional practice of New Engineers and reflection is regarded an important skill in this respect (Rogers, 2001, see also Yost et al., 2000).

Skills in reflection do not come naturally, but can be trained (e.g. Gün, 2011; Kori et al., 2014; Russel, 2005). However, reflection is considered challenging for students and, for different reasons, support is needed (Abou Baker El-Dib, 2007; Lee, 2005). For example, reflection requires creative thinking and seeing alternatives, which might be challenging for students (e.g. Leijen et al. 2012). Obviously, it is not enough to tell students to just “go and reflect” (Welch, 1999).

Kori et al. (2014) reviewed several studies that aimed at supporting reflection in technology-enhanced learning environments. Several support measures were identified, ranging from videos, blogs and portfolios, to prompts and guiding questions, and peer/teacher interactions. Their research showed that these measures all have their benefits, but that this depends on the type of learning environment and the specific reflection activity. The authors also state that measures to evaluate the effect of the support measures in the studies they included in their review lacked in terms of validity and reliability.

For the underlying study, we based our intervention on the work of Ash and Clayton (2004) on *articulated learning*. On the one hand, their approach aligns with what Poldner et al. (2011) considered to be common to reflection definitions; 1) reflections are directed at something, 2) are part of a cyclical process, 3) can vary in strength, 4) include an affective component and 5) include an intention to change based on newly acquired insights. Also, there is evidence that their approach can foster quality of reflection (Ash et al., 2005) as measured with rubrics for assessing quality (or strength) of reflections. The rubric that was developed for this study was further inspired by Kember et al. (2008). Other means to assess the quality of reflection can be found in Dymont and O'Connell (2011).

On the other hand, their approach to support reflection is straightforward, it makes use of scaffolding questions to structure student reflections and stimulates students to think deeply about their object of reflection. Peer and teacher interaction, and feedback cycles (Ash et al., 2005) might add to the training effect, but in this case we decided not to add more to the intervention group' workload than strictly necessary because of the Covid-19 situation (the intervention was part of their curricular work). However, to increase the impact of the intervention, examples of reflections of different quality levels were provided, with an explanation of why, according to specific criteria, the example would fall into a certain reflection quality level category. This add-on is based on the well-established effect of learning from examples (see e.g. Hoogerheide & Roelle, 2020).

Up until the moment of the current study, the ATLAS program offered support to first-year students in writing their SERs by providing two pages of written instructions and one 1.5-hour *lectorial* (interactive lecture, similar to a workshop) on the nature of reflection and self-evaluation. However, the effect of this support, especially with respect to reflection, was not reflected in their SERs. Teacher-assessors generally noted the poor quality of reflection displayed in the SERs, but also appeared to use different criteria for assessing the SER reflections. Typically, the assessment manuals for assessors contained no information about criteria to use in providing feedback on the quality of reflection. Moreover, students did not seem to be aware what was expected of them with respect to reflection. These observations formed the motive for this study, the underlying problem being unclarity surrounding what constitutes proper reflection, both on the students' and the teachers' side. Without such clarity, the conditions needed to develop reflection skills are at least suboptimal. Typically, quality of reflections in the SERs remained stable throughout the program.

1.2 Research question

This study was part of a larger project that contained five studies. The research questions of the overall project were 1) What would be an appropriate reflection method for first-year ATLAS students that includes both support measures and feedback criteria? 2) What is the effect of an intervention targeted at fostering quality of reflection? and 3) What is the level of perceived usefulness and value of the

proposed reflection method on which the intervention was based for students and teacher-assessors? In this paper, results of a study that targeted the second question will be reported.

1.3 Intervention design

A qualitative pilot test made clear that students tend to focus their reflections on their academic performance. In this, the distinction between reflection and self-evaluation becomes blurry, which is corroborated by several student statements that point to confusion about the distinction between them. Although most students feel that they can meet expectations regarding reflection, the majority states to need additional educational support. Clear instructions, templates and examples, feedback cycles and interactive SER writing sessions were suggested.

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, education went online during the study and the first-year students were under quite some strain already. Therefore, it was decided to keep the intervention low-key. A Reflection Guide (based on the work of Ash & Clayton, 2004) was provided with clear instructions, scaffolding questions that served as a template to structure reflections and to stimulate students to think deeply about a reflection object, quality criteria (rubric), and examples of low to high quality reflections with fictitious examples that highlighted the criteria. These ingredients mostly aligned with the needs identified in the pilot study, with the exception of including peer/teacher interactions and feedback cycles, for reasons mentioned before. The Reflection Guide was written to be self-contained as additional instruction to write the SER, but the content of the guide was also discussed in two non-mandatory online lectorials of approximately 1.5 hours. The first lectorial focused in the students' task of writing reflections in their SERs, the second one repeated the first (on purpose; very few students showed up the first time), but also elaborated on the quality criteria and the reflection examples. There was room for questions in both lectorials.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Participants

The intervention group consisted of 29 first-year ATLAS students in their first semester (Class of 2023). There were 14 females, 58.6% of the whole class was of native Dutch origin. For comparison, the first semester SERs of 33 students of the Class of 2022 were used (also 14 females, 60.6% of the whole class was of native Dutch origin¹). Students in both cohorts were admitted on the basis of the same admission criteria. Students from both cohorts that failed their semester were excluded from analysis.

¹ The author could not find evidence to support the idea that quality of reflection is affected by cultural differences. ATLAS is an international study program, these data are included to show to what extent the intervention and comparison group could be compared.

2.2 Materials

To assess the quality of reflection displayed in the SERs of the students, a rubric was constructed based on the levels of reflection described in the Reflection Guide. There are four levels of reflection and the rubric also contains intermediate levels, see Table 1 below. The parameters that define the level of reflection are: 1) understanding of the critical incident in term of the student's learning (*understanding dimension*); 2) implication of the learning for other situations in which it might apply (*transfer dimension*); 3) the personal impact or - significance of the incident (*personal dimension*) and 4) the extent to which the incident has had implications for future goals or behaviours (*future dimension*). The highest level, which is not common according to Kember et al. (2008), also includes evidence of a fundamental change in perspective.

2.3 Procedure

SERs were retrieved from the program's data base. The principal researcher first identified the different reflections in the SERs and then assigned a level to each of them on the basis of the rubric. An excerpt was considered a reflection when 1) students apparently "looked inside", and apparently thought about an experience or 2) when the excerpt was headed with "reflection" (this was common in the intervention group because they were instructed to structure their SERs in separate reflection and self-evaluation paragraphs). Students in the intervention group were instructed to write three reflections, while students in the comparison group could write as many as they liked. In this group, when students wrote more than three reflections, the three highest-scoring reflections were taken as units of analysis.

2.4 Data analysis

Level 1 reflections were assigned a score of 1, 1+ reflections were assigned with a score of 1.5, level 2 reflections were assigned a score of 2, etc. Mean reflection level was calculated by averaging the scores of the three reflections with the highest individual scores. Difference in mean quality of reflection was tested with a T-test for independent samples. Possible effects of gender and nationality (Dutch/foreign) were controlled for.

Table 1. scoring rubric quality of reflection

Level 1: Non- reflection
The intended reflection shows no evidence of the student attempting to reach understanding of a critical incident or significant learning experience. The student is basically evaluating his or learning on a general level, the learning is not related to any other situation in which it might apply. The reflection is not personal, it could have been written by any student. No implications for future goals or behaviours mentioned.
Level 1+: the reflection scores higher on certain criteria, but not enough for the reflection to be fully classified on the next level.
Level 2: Understanding
A critical incident or learning experience is described to a certain extent, and the student is able to explain its meaning, but does not relate it to any other situation in which it might apply. Also, it does not become clear in what way the experience matters for the student personally, or how it affected future goals or behaviours.
Level 2+: the reflection scores higher on certain criteria, but not enough for the reflection to be fully classified on the next level.
Level 3: Reflection
A critical incident is described clearly, and the student is able to explain its meaning and how it relates to other situations in which it might apply. It is also clear how and why the experience has mattered to the student on a personal level.
Level 3+: the reflection scores higher on certain criteria, but not enough for the reflection to be fully classified on the next level.
Level 4: Critical reflection
All of the above (level 3), while it is also clear how the incident has affected the student's future goals or behaviours. In addition, there is clear evidence of a change in perspective over a fundamental belief.

Note: criteria relate to four dimensions: *understanding, transfer, personal and future*

3. Results & Discussion

First, it must be noted that students in the comparison group delivered reflections that were assessable with the criteria in the Reflection Guide. This indicates that they, to a certain extent, had similar ideas about what reflection entails compared to the intervention group. Therefore, it seems fair to compare the groups.

Average level of reflection in the intervention group was 2.0 (SD: .56, range 1.17 – 2.67). In the comparison group, this was 1.3 (SD: .30, range 1.0 – 2.17). A T-test for

Table 2. Percentages of reflections at different levels in comparison and intervention group

		Reflection levels							
		SRs	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4
Comparison group	T1		39.4	33.3	21.2	6.1	-	-	-
	(n = 33)	T2	54.5	36.4	6.1	3.0	-	-	-
		T3	90.9	9.1	-	-	-	-	-
Intervention group	T1		-	13.8	24.1	20.7	34.5	6.9	-
	(n = 29)	T2	13.8	27.6	31.0	13.8	10.3	3.4	-
		T3	34.5	31.0	17.2	13.8	3.4	-	-

Note: SRs: three strongest reflections found in the semester 1 Self-Evaluation Reports of the participants (T1 – T3). Reflection levels: 1 = lowest, 4 = highest (see also Table 1).

independent samples showed this difference to be significant ($t = -6.64$, $df = 60$, $p < .001$); compared to the students in the comparison group, students in the intervention group reflected on a higher level. To provide more insight into the effect of the intervention, see Table 2. As can be seen, across the three strongest reflections (SRs) found in the SERs of the students in the comparison and intervention group, variation in the intervention group is stronger, with fewer reflections at level 1 and 1.5 and more at level 2 – 3. In the comparison group, no reflections at level 3 and onward were found, while in the intervention group, these were quite common. No effects of gender were found. In the intervention group, difference in reflection levels between Dutch students and foreign students approached significance favouring the Dutch students (means were 2.2, SD: .54 vs. 1.8, SD: .53, sign. $< .06$ for the Dutch and foreign students respectively), however these groups were relatively small (17 vs. 13 students, respectively). Average number of reflections per group was 5.5 (SD: 3.1) for the comparison group and 4.8 (SD: 4.9) for the intervention group. This difference was not significant. Apparently, students in the intervention group tended to produce more reflections than the minimum of three that was expected.

In conclusion, despite being low-key due to Covid-19, the intervention was successful in its aim to foster the quality of reflection in the SERs of the students. In two additional studies that were part of the overall project, both students and teachers valued the reflection method, implicating that there is support base for further implementation. The results also support earlier findings by Ash et al. (2005) and Kori et al. (2014), showing that quality of reflection can be enhanced by intervention. This implicates that, with relatively simple means (scaffolding questions

and examples), educators can foster their students' reflective abilities. Adding feedback cycles and (peer-) interaction can further strengthen and reinforce quality of reflection.

Two important shortcomings of this study will now be addressed. Firstly, the study uses a between subject design to study the effect of the intervention. A pre-post control group design would have been a more valid test, because now we must assume that the intervention and comparison group were comparable in their initial reflective ability. However, splitting the Class of 2023 in two to create a control and comparison group was not deemed ethical because students might profit from the intervention in terms of study progress (a SER rewrite is needed when the quality of reflection is not up to par). Moreover, collecting base-rate information was deemed inappropriate because of the serious workload the students had. On the other hand, the comparison and intervention group were comparable in terms of gender distribution, Dutch/foreign nationality distribution and ATLAS admission criteria. Of course, the relevancy of these characteristics for reflective ability is not known (in fact, results showed gender and nationality were unrelated to mean level of reflection quality) and measures that could predict reflection ability were not taken, but overall it is assumed the comparison was fair.

Secondly, the reflections in the SERs were identified and coded by the main researcher. Although the coding rubric is deemed elaborate and insightful, a certain expectation on his hand could have influenced the results. Involving a second coder to assess the interrater reliability of the coding protocol would have solved this problem.

Further research and development could focus on testing the effect of a more elaborate intervention including feedback cycles and peer/teacher interaction.

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